

National
COVID
Cohort
Collaborative

Economic Instability

A Year 1 Quarter 4 PASC RECOVER EHR-Based Query Report from N3C

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Minor corrections in **Results: Trends Observed**

Overview

OBJECTIVE

The goals of this electronic health record (EHR) query are to investigate:

- 1) Amongst known COVID-19 patients, who is experiencing new Economic Instability?
- 2) Amongst COVID-19 patients with documented Long COVID, who is experiencing new Economic Instability?

DATA SOURCE

The National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C) hosts nearly 20 billion rows of medical record data, providing a rich resource for big data analysis. Data are from version 97 of the N3C data enclave, released on October 20th, 2022 and include medical data from the study period: 3/1/2020 – 10/29/2022. The size of each patient cohort used in our analyses is reported in detail below.

APPROACH

To answer this query using electronic health record (EHR) data in N3C, we utilized codes recorded in patient records that indicate possible new Economic Instability to define our primary outcomes. These code sets (defined in detail below) include those that show a change from private insurance to Medicaid, loss of insurance, new food insecurity, new housing instability, or new disability. Because not all sites contributing data provided insurance data and not all sites provided patient zip codes for area level features, a variety of statistical analyses were performed based on the available datasets to understand the relationship between individual and area level characteristics and the likelihood of new Economic Instability. Because patterns differ by location, the analyses were conditioned on site where the data was collected.

RESULTS

The results of primary and secondary analyses are described in detail at the end of this report and should be considered alongside the limitations noted in the next section. Race/ethnicity, age, and rural vs. urban home address were predictive of new Economic Instability. Specifically the following groups all had higher odds of new Economic Instability post-COVID-19: Black or African American Non Hispanics, Hispanic or Latinos, patients ages 50-69, and patients with a rural¹ home address. Furthermore, new Economic Instability was more prevalent in the sub-group of COVID-19 patients with documented Long COVID. In the primary analysis, the rate of new Economic Instability in the Long COVID Patients was 6 times greater than the COVID-19 patients at large. In the secondary analysis, which included a subset of sites and added insurance data, the rate of new economic instability was 19 times greater in the Long COVID subcohort.

LIMITATIONS

It is important to note that EHR data are captured in the course of patient care and are not specifically designed to answer research questions or to capture measures of economic instability. Data on economic instability are highly inconsistent, contributing to missing or incomplete data that can seriously bias such an analysis. EHR data are not necessarily representative of the population from which they were collected, and we are further limited to data captured in the medical record at participating medical centers. We recognize that this provides an incomplete picture of the United States at large. Multiple factors can impact how people choose whether they seek care and where they get their care. The data we have only provides a single race and ethnicity value for each patient and reflects these values as recorded in the medical record. Social Determinants of Health features captured by the US Census² do not reflect the individual, but rather their area at large. These are included in some analyses below to control for area level features and should only be interpreted as contextual, meaning that a feature like percent poverty in a zip code does not measure the patient's poverty, but rather poverty in their area.

There are several limitations to consider specifically related to COVID-19 and Long Covid. The exact timing of economic instability vis-à-vis COVID or Long COVID conditions cannot be ascertained from the medical record. For this analysis, the first record of COVID-19 was used as an index date for this condition. Long COVID is very under-recorded in the medical record at this time. We limited our Long COVID analyses to just the patients where a specific code was entered in the chart by a clinician, thus focusing those analyses to patients where the condition has been recognized and documented³. People with a documented COVID test and with providers who are knowledgeable about and willing to use the new Long COVID ICD code may be more economically privileged than those without, which could bias our analysis towards these groups.

CONCLUSIONS

These analyses suggest that certain demographic groups are more vulnerable to post-COVID-19 new Economic Instability related to housing, food, loss of insurance, or disability. It also suggests that patients with Long COVID may be experiencing more new economic instability. Given the described limitations of observational health record data, we

recommend conducting similar analyses on other datasets that explicitly measure these variables.

Definitions

STUDY COHORT

We focus on two cohorts - COVID positive (Cohort A) and Long COVID positive (Cohort B) groups each defined by the below lab results and diagnosis/reimbursement codes.

- **COHORT A: COVID-19 positive:**
 - Positive results from a PCR or AG SARS-COV-2 lab test or
 - Diagnosis code of U07.1 (COVID-19)
- **COHORT B: Long COVID positive:**
 - Diagnosis code of U09.9 (Post-infectious condition after COVID-19, unspecified) after COVID-19 infection and AFTER Oct 1, 2021 or
 - Diagnosis code of B94.8 (Sequelae of other specified infectious and parasitic diseases) after COVID-19 infection and BEFORE Oct 1, 2021

RACE AND ETHNICITY CATEGORIES

Definitions for Racial and Ethnic categories is as follows:

- **American Indian or Alaska Native.** A person having origins in any of the original peoples of North and South America (including Central America), and who maintains tribal affiliation or community attachment.
- **Asian.** A person having origins in any of the original peoples of the Far East, Southeast Asia, or the Indian subcontinent including, for example, Cambodia, China, India, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Pakistan, the Philippine Islands, Thailand, and Vietnam.
- **Black or African American.** A person having origins in any of the black racial groups of Africa. Terms such as "Haitian" or "Negro" can be used in addition to "Black or African American."
- **Hispanic or Latino.** A person of Cuban, Mexican, Puerto Rican, South or Central American, or other Spanish culture or origin, regardless of race. The term, "Spanish origin," can be used in addition to "Hispanic or Latino."
- **Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander.** A person having origins in any of the original peoples of Hawaii, Guam, Samoa, or other Pacific Islands.
- **White.** A person having origins in any of the original peoples of Europe, the Middle East, or North Africa.

NEW ECONOMIC INSTABILITY

Any one of the following metrics as documented in the electronic health record. Note that NEW is evaluated by checking for each type of Economic Instability up to and at the time of the COVID index event and comparing to NEW information. If a patient had any of the prior categories up to and at the time of index event, they are NOT flagged as new events.

- New food insecurity
- New housing instability
- New documented disability
- Change in insurance payor (private pay to Medicaid) or loss of insurance

GEOGRAPHICALLY-ASSOCIATED SOCIAL DETERMINANTS OF HEALTH (SDOH)

Public SDOH metrics² associated with the patient based on the patient's zip code.

- The following US Census data, collected by Zip Code Tabulation Area (ZCTA), was mapped to each patient using their home address:
 - ZCTA poverty status: % of population living at or below the poverty level where poverty status is determined based on poverty status of householder
 - ZCTA unemployment status: % of population aged 16 and older who are unemployed
 - ZCTA education_bachelors_degree: % of population 25 years and older with a bachelor's degree
 - ZCTA citizen_US: % of total population who are US citizens
- 'Urban/Rural flag': The rural-urban commuting area (RUCA) codes classify U.S¹. census tracts using measures of population density, urbanization, and daily commuting. From **Appendix Table 1**, 1-3 are binned into urban, 4-10 are binned into rural.

LONG COVID SUB-PHENOTYPES

Long COVID sub-phenotypes was defined as previously described⁴, trained on a cohort of patients who were known to have a u09.9 diagnosis and selected from data partners that provided at least 300 U09.9 patients and an average of at least seven HPO (Human Phenotype Ontology) terms per patient. A semantic unsupervised learning clustering technique was used to cluster the patients into six groups. The clusters include non-uniform frequencies of symptoms and clinical findings across an array of features, spanning constitutional/systemic symptoms and pain, cardiac, respiratory, gastrointestinal, and neurologic symptom domains. In order to label a patient as a Long COVID sub-phenotype or not, the patient must meet the above criteria. The clusters are labeled here based on the majority of codes related to that cluster. The clustering algorithm was trained only on the U09.9 diagnosis code and was also not rerun on the v97 released data, therefore we observe no clusters assigned to patients with B94.8 code and also for some with U09.9 diagnosis code. Further, cluster 5 was removed from our analysis as it includes only one patient from our Long COVID study cohort.

Group 1: multisystem+lab abnormalities

Group 2: pulmonary

Group 3: neuropsychiatric

Group 4: cardiovascular

Group 5: pain/fatigue (dropped due to insufficient representation)

Group 6: multisystem+pain

Methods

VARIABLE SELECTION

A variety of personal events coded in the medical record can be a proxy for Economic Instability such as disability, food instability, housing instability, and a change from private to Medicaid insurance or a loss of insurance. For the purposes of this query, we only used these indicators as the dependent variables in our analyses if they were new after the first diagnosis or lab confirmation of COVID-19 in the medical record. If a patient had an indicator prior to, or at the time of the initial COVID-19 index event, then we do not consider any of the same events after that time to be new. The concept sets (lists of relevant medical record codes) used for the Economic Instability variables were built in partnership with the N3C Social Determinants of Health (SDoH) Domain Team leads and were informed by review of relevant Value Set Authority Center⁵ concept sets as well as the Gravity Project⁶.

Standard demographic features (age, sex, and race/ethnicity) were included as independent variables. Age was binned by decade in order to simplify the interpretation of this continuous feature. Sex reflects the values of “male” or “female” as recorded in the medical record and patients without either value recorded (<20) were dropped from the analysis. Race/ethnicity variable categories and definitions are adapted as per the NIH definitions in order to maintain the uniformity and comparability of data⁸. The category “Other non-hispanic” includes Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander Non-Hispanic and American Indian or Alaska Native Non-Hispanic due to low numbers (<10) in Long COVID cohort.

Some sites provide five digit zip codes for the patient data in the secure enclave, enabling us to determine if the patient is from a rural area and also to include certain SDoH features at the area code level. These variables provide context about features in the area where the patient lives. Understanding Economic Instability in light of these features is important for uncovering any strong trends related to social features such as area-level rates of citizenship, college degrees, unemployment, and poverty. Data for these features came from the US Census Data² and were also selected in partnership with the N3C SDoH Domain Team.

Long COVID is a complex syndrome with diverse manifestations still being studied by the medical community. In an effort to define possible sub-phenotypes of Long COVID, N3C researchers built a clustering algorithm using features of Long COVID patients⁴ and assigning people to the cluster that most closely represented their symptomatology. These clusters were used as features in our Long COVID sub-cohort analyses in order to investigate potential relationships between sub-phenotypes and the likelihood of new Economic Instability.

STATISTICAL MODEL

Generalized Estimating Equations is a method used for modeling clustered data⁵. Our goal is to account for correlations with the subjects across different sites and then make inferences. This is important given the variability of data capture and data mapping practices between different

hospitals, as well as the differences in patient populations across N3C.

PRIMARY ANALYSIS (BASE DEFINITION OF NEW ECONOMIC INSTABILITY)

Amongst our known COVID-19 (Cohort A), who is experiencing new Economic Instability? We have performed a logistic regression for each outcome individually plus a combined “any new post-COVID Economic Instability” (any new disability, housing instability, and food insecurity) as the dependent variable with demographic as independent variables. We utilized a GEEGLM model for logistic regression with “data_partner_id” as a controlling parameter in order to condition the analysis on the institutions/sites. We performed the same analysis with a sub-cohort of patients with documented Long COVID (Cohort B).

SECONDARY ANALYSIS (EXTENDED DEFINITION OF NEW ECONOMIC INSTABILITY)

Amongst our known COVID-19 (Cohort A), who is experiencing new Economic Instability? We have performed a logistic regression for each outcome individually plus a combined “any new post-COVID Economic Instability” (any new disability, housing instability, food insecurity, **and change from private insurance to Medicaid or loss of insurance**) as the dependent variable with demographic as independent variables. We utilized a GEEGLM model for logistic regression with “data_partner_id” as a controlling parameter in order to condition the analysis on the institutions/sites. Perform the same analysis with a sub-cohort of patients with documented Long COVID (Cohort B).

SITE INCLUSION CRITERIA + EXCLUSION CRITERIA

We do not want to include sites that do not report the features we are interested in for our analyses*.

- **PRIMARY ANALYSIS:** Include only sites that report ALL of the following features in their patient data as defined above:
 - New food insecurity
 - New housing instability
 - New documented disability
 - Long COVID
- **SECONDARY ANALYSIS:** Include only sites that report ALL of the following features in their patient data as defined above:
 - New food insecurity
 - New housing instability
 - New documented disability
 - Long COVID
 - Change in insurance payor (private pay to Medicaid) or loss of insurance
- **PASC RECOVER** quality filter for sites:
 - (1) should not shift dates by more than 30 days

- (2) should have serum creatinine and lymphocyte count results for at least 25% of hospitalizations
- (3) should not have >10% of their hospitalizations where the COVID-19 index date is more than 200 days after the visit start date.

*Because insurance data is only available from a small number of sites, we will conduct a sub-analysis that includes only those sites, rather than imposing this restriction on our main analysis.

COHORT SELECTION FLOWCHART

CELL SIZE AND PATIENT PRIVACY PROTECTION

In order to comply with N3C data use policies, any cell sizes under 20 were suppressed

Results

RESULTS FROM PRIMARY ANALYSIS (58 sites): Economic Instability (New disability, food instability, or housing instability)

Table 1 (below) shows the number of COVID positive patients, broken down by demographics, instability variables and distribution in geographically-associated Social Determinants of Health of COVID positive patients (COHORT A) included in our primary analysis. It also includes other statistics such as percentages, and first and third quartiles.

Characteristic	Missing # (%)	Overall # (%)	Economic Instability (EI) Status	
			Without new EI # (%)	With new EI # (%)
N = # COVID positive (COHORT A)		5428472	5408571	19901
Age groups	68838			
<20		1023468 (19.1)	1018957 (19.1)	4511 (22.9)
20-29		822425 (15.3)	820137 (15.4)	2288 (11.6)
30-39		825196 (15.4)	822619 (15.4)	2577 (13.1)
40-49		754689 (14.1)	752030 (14.1)	2659 (13.5)
50-59		750227 (14.0)	747083 (14.0)	3144 (15.9)
60-69		609146 (11.4)	606523 (11.4)	2623 (13.3)
70-79		366349 (6.8)	364991 (6.8)	1358 (6.9)
80+		208134 (3.9)	207579 (3.9)	555 (2.8)
Sex				
Male		2428707 (44.7)	2419641 (44.7)	9066 (45.6)
Female		2999765 (55.3)	2988930 (55.3)	10835 (54.4)
Race ethnicity				
White Non-Hispanic		3383049 (62.3)	3373077 (62.4)	9972 (50.1)
Black or African American Non-Hispanic		742678 (13.7)	737328 (13.6)	5350 (26.9)
Hispanic or Latino Any Race		650219 (12.0)	647169 (12.0)	3050 (15.3)
Asian Non-Hispanic		98812 (1.8)	98446 (1.8)	366 (1.8)
Other Non-Hispanic		163353 (3.0)	163073 (3.0)	280 (1.4)
Unknown		390361 (7.2)	389478 (7.2)	883 (4.4)
EI variables				
new_disability_post_COVID		5591 (0.1)		5591 (28.1)
new_foodinsecurity_post_COVID		2783 (0.1)		2783 (14.0)

new_housinginstability_post_COVID		12240 (0.2)		12240 (61.5)
SDOH Zip level (%)				
citizen_US, median [Q1,Q3]	1275902	93.0 [87.0,96.7]	93.0 [87.0,96.7]	91.3 [84.3,95.9]
education_bachelors_degree, median [Q1,Q3]	1275869	17.7 [11.9,26.0]	17.7 [11.9,26.0]	18.0 [12.6,24.7]
poverty_status, median [Q1,Q3]	1278110	11.7 [7.2,17.6]	11.7 [7.2,17.6]	13.8 [8.7,20.0]
unemployment_status_age_16plus, median [Q1,Q3]	1276040	4.4 [3.3,6.1]	4.4 [3.3,6.1]	4.6 [3.5,6.8]
rural_flag, n (%)	1275386	746996 (18.0)	743517 (18.0)	3479 (20.2)

Table 1. COHORT A for PRIMARY ANALYSIS: Characteristics of patients by Economic Instability outcome in COVID positive group

Figure 1 (below) shows the results of a logistic regression that includes demographic information as independent variables and examines how they impact Economic Instability post covid. See the discussion section of this report for observations about these results.

Figure 1: GEEGLM model forest plots for primary analysis (COHORT A)

The statistical analysis shown in Figure 2 (below) is similar to that represented by Figure 1, except that the feature set used in the Figure 2 analysis also includes Social Determinants of Health and a rurality flag (based on the patient's zip code) as independent variables in examining how they impact Economic Instability post covid. See the discussion section of this report for observations about these results.

Figure 2: GEEGLM model forest plots for primary analysis (COHORT A) with SDoH features

Table 2 (below) shows the number of Long COVID patients, broken down by demographics, instability variables and distribution in geographically-associated Social determinants of health of Long COVID patients (COHORT B) included in our primary analysis, along with percentages, quartiles, and cluster assignment information.

Characteristic	Missing # (%)	Overall # (%)	Economic Instability (EI) Status	
			Without new EI # (%)	With new EI # (%)
N = # Long COVID positive (COHORT B)		35003	34333	670
Age groups	490			
<20		1702 (4.9)	1663 (4.9)	39 (5.8)
20-29		2198 (6.4)	2164 (6.4)	34 (5.1)
30-39		4483 (13.0)	4392 (13.0)	91 (13.6)
40-49		6422 (18.6)	6310 (18.6)	112 (16.8)
50-59		7467 (21.6)	7297 (21.6)	170 (25.4)
60-69		6660 (19.3)	6519 (19.3)	141 (21.1)
70-79		3799 (11.0)	3744 (11.1)	55 (8.2)
80+		1782 (5.2)	1756 (5.2)	26 (3.9)
Sex				
Male		12930 (36.9)	12655 (36.9)	275 (41.0)
Female		22073 (63.1)	21678 (63.1)	395 (59.0)
Race ethnicity				
White Non-Hispanic		22541 (64.4)	22166 (64.6)	375 (56.0)
Black or African American Non-Hispanic		5697 (16.3)	5532 (16.1)	165 (24.6)
Hispanic or Latino Any Race		4105 (11.7)	4027 (11.7)	78 (11.6)
Asian Non-Hispanic		655 (1.9)	643 (1.9)	<20
Other Non-Hispanic		418 (1.2)	407 (1.2)	<20
Unknown		1587 (4.5)	1558 (4.5)	29 (4.3)
EI variables				
new_disability_post_COVID		212 (0.6)		212 (31.6)
new_foodinsecurity_post_COVID		113 (0.3)		113 (16.9)
new_housinginstability_post_COVID		379 (1.1)		379 (56.6)
SDOH Zip level (%)				
citizen_US, median [Q1,Q3]	8221	91.9 [85.8,95.8]	91.9 [85.9,95.8]	91.1 [85.0,95.7]

education_bachelors_degree, median [Q1,Q3]	8220	19.3 [12.8,27.6]	19.3 [12.8,27.6]	17.9 [12.3,24.8]
poverty_status, median [Q1,Q3]	8224	11.3 [6.9,17.7]	11.3 [6.9,17.6]	13.6 [8.3,19.9]
unemployment_status_age_16plus, median [Q1,Q3]	8224	4.5 [3.3,6.3]	4.5 [3.3,6.3]	4.6 [3.5,6.8]
rural_flag, n (%)	8217	3910 (14.6)	3796 (14.5)	114 (19.1)
Cluster				
cluster_1		5070 (14.5)	4888 (14.2)	182 (27.2)
cluster_2		1595 (4.6)	1575 (4.6)	20 (3.0)
cluster_3		1219 (3.5)	1177 (3.4)	42 (6.3)
cluster_4		2240 (6.4)	2197 (6.4)	43 (6.4)
cluster_6		5201 (14.9)	5073 (14.8)	128 (19.1)
no_cluster_assigned		19678 (56.2)	19423 (56.6)	255 (38.1)

Table 2. COHORT B for PRIMARY ANALYSIS: Characteristics of patients by Economic Instability outcome in Long COVID positive group

Figure 3 (below) shows the results of a logistic regression that includes demographic information as independent variables and examines how they impact Economic Instability post covid among the Long COVID patients (COHORT B). See the discussion section of this report for observations about these results.

Figure 3: GEEGLM model forest plots for primary analysis (COHORT-B)

The statistical analysis shown in Figure 4 (below) is similar to that represented by Figure 3, except that the feature set used in the Figure 4 analysis also includes Social Determinants of Health and a rurality flag (based on the patient's zip code) as independent variables in examining how they impact new Economic Instability in the Long COVID sub-cohort. See the discussion section of this report for observations about these results.

Figure 4: GEEGLM model forest plots for primary analysis (COHORT-B) with SDoH features

RESULTS FROM THE SECONDARY ANALYSIS (16 sites): Economic Instability

(Includes change from private insurance to Medicaid or loss of INSURANCE)

The secondary analysis limits to sites that report insurance data in relation to patient visits. In the secondary analysis, new Economic Instability includes Change to Medicaid or Loss of Insurance.

Table 3 (below) shows the number of COVID positive patients, broken down by demographics, instability variables and distribution in geographically-associated Social Determinants of Health of COVID positive patients (COHORT A) included in our secondary analysis. It also includes other statistics such as percentages, and first and third quartiles.

Characteristic	Missing # (%)	Overall # (%)	Economic Instability (EI) Status	
			Without new EI # (%)	With new EI # (%)
N = # COVID positive (COHORT A)		1379504	1145088	234416
Age groups	63167			
<20		237952 (18.1)	215778 (19.1)	22174 (11.8)
20-29		192397 (14.6)	163108 (14.5)	29289 (15.5)
30-39		204749 (15.6)	171266 (15.2)	33483 (17.8)
40-49		193630 (14.7)	158954 (14.1)	34676 (18.4)
50-59		193009 (14.7)	158869 (14.1)	34140 (18.1)
60-69		156192 (11.9)	133012 (11.8)	23180 (12.3)
70-79		91672 (7.0)	83423 (7.4)	8249 (4.4)
80+		46736 (3.6)	43562 (3.9)	3174 (1.7)
Sex				
Male		595949 (43.2)	505887 (44.2)	90062 (38.4)
Female		783555 (56.8)	639201 (55.8)	144354 (61.6)
Race ethnicity				
White Non-Hispanic		660155 (47.9)	562600 (49.1)	97555 (41.6)
Black or African American Non-Hispanic		285020 (20.7)	232381 (20.3)	52639 (22.5)
Hispanic or Latino Any Race		257449 (18.7)	194636 (17.0)	62813 (26.8)
Asian Non-Hispanic		42350 (3.1)	35715 (3.1)	6635 (2.8)
Other Non-Hispanic		19294 (1.4)	16831 (1.5)	2463 (1.1)
Unknown		115236 (8.4)	102925 (9.0)	12311 (5.3)
EI variables				

new_disability_post_COVID		1505 (0.1)		1505 (0.6)
new_foodinsecurity_post_COVID		958 (0.1)		958 (0.4)
new_housinginstability_post_COVID		4376 (0.3)		4376 (1.9)
change_or_loss_of_insurance, n (%)		228965 (16.6)		228965 (97.7)
SDOH Zip level (%)				
citizen_US, median [Q1,Q3]	307342	90.5 [82.5,94.8]	90.8 [83.6,94.9]	88.4 [78.1,93.7]
education_bachelors_degree, median [Q1,Q3]	307333	19.1 [12.1,27.5]	19.3 [12.2,27.7]	18.0 [11.2,26.0]
poverty_status, median [Q1,Q3]	307739	14.2 [8.2,19.5]	14.0 [8.1,19.2]	15.1 [8.9,21.4]
unemployment_status_age_16plus, median [Q1,Q3]	307392	5.0 [3.6,7.0]	4.9 [3.6,7.0]	5.3 [4.0,7.5]
rural_flag, n (%)	307248	121173 (11.3)	103872 (11.7)	17301 (9.5)

Table 3. COHORT A for SECONDARY ANALYSIS: Characteristics of patients by Economic Instability outcome INCLUDING change or loss of insurance in COVID positive group

Figure 5 (below) shows the results of a logistic regression that includes demographic information as independent variables and examines how they impact Economic Instability post covid. See the discussion section of this report for observations about these results.

Figure 5: GEEGLM model forest plots for secondary analysis (COHORT-A)

The statistical analysis shown in Figure 6 (below) is similar to that represented by Figure 5, except that the feature set used in the Figure 6 analysis also includes Social Determinants of Health and a rurality flag (based on the patient's zip code) as independent variables in examining how they impact Economic Instability post covid. See the discussion section of this report for observations about these results.

Figure 6: GEEGLM model forest plots for secondary analysis (COHORT-A) with SDoH

Table 4 (below) shows the number of Long COVID patients, broken down by demographics, instability variables and distribution in geographically-associated Social determinants of health of Long COVID patients (COHORT B) included in our primary analysis, along with percentages, quartiles, and cluster assignment information.

Characteristic	Missing # (%)	Overall # (%)	Economic Instability (EI) Status	
			Without new EI # (%)	With new EI # (%)
N = # Long COVID positive (COHORT B)		13576	9461	4115
Age groups	478			
<20		629 (4.8)	490 (5.2)	139 (3.8)
20-29		814 (6.2)	557 (5.9)	257 (7.0)
30-39		1700 (13.0)	1171 (12.4)	529 (14.3)
40-49		2638 (20.1)	1727 (18.4)	911 (24.7)
50-59		2932 (22.4)	2012 (21.4)	920 (25.0)
60-69		2458 (18.8)	1823 (19.4)	635 (17.2)
70-79		1345 (10.3)	1125 (12.0)	220 (6.0)
80+		582 (4.4)	506 (5.4)	76 (2.1)
Sex				
Male		4802 (35.4)	3480 (36.8)	1322 (32.1)
Female		8774 (64.6)	5981 (63.2)	2793 (67.9)
Race ethnicity				
White Non-Hispanic		7937 (58.5)	5668 (59.9)	2269 (55.1)
Black or African American Non-Hispanic		2639 (19.4)	1819 (19.2)	820 (19.9)
Hispanic or Latino Any Race		1945 (14.3)	1228 (13.0)	717 (17.4)
Asian Non-Hispanic		297 (2.2)	226 (2.4)	71 (1.7)
Other Non-Hispanic		256 (1.9)	196 (2.1)	60 (1.5)
Unknown		502 (3.7)	324 (3.4)	178 (4.3)
EI variables				
new_disability_post_COVID		55 (0.4)		55 (1.3)
new_foodinsecurity_post_COVID		31 (0.2)		31 (0.8)
new_housinginstability_post_COVID		146 (1.1)		146 (3.5)
change_or_loss_of_insurance, n (%)		3934 (29.0)		3934 (95.6)
SDOH Zip level (%)				

citizen_US, median [Q1,Q3]	2011	91.5 [85.4,95.2]	91.7 [86.2,95.4]	91.2 [84.3,94.8]
education_bachelors_degree, median [Q1,Q3]	2010	17.8 [11.6,26.4]	18.0 [11.8,27.1]	17.3 [11.2,25.7]
poverty_status, median [Q1,Q3]	2012	14.0 [8.4,19.6]	13.9 [8.1,19.4]	14.3 [9.1,20.0]
unemployment_status_age_16plus, median [Q1,Q3]	2011	5.0 [3.5,7.0]	4.8 [3.4,7.0]	5.2 [3.9,7.1]
rural_flag, n (%)	2010	1875 (16.2)	1362 (16.9)	513 (14.7)
Cluster				
cluster_1		1926 (14.2)	1418 (15.0)	508 (12.3)
cluster_2		521 (3.8)	397 (4.2)	124 (3.0)
cluster_3		394 (2.9)	301 (3.2)	93 (2.3)
cluster_4		722 (5.3)	538 (5.7)	184 (4.5)
cluster_6		1626 (12.0)	1205 (12.7)	421 (10.2)
no_cluster_assigned		8387 (61.8)	5602 (59.2)	2785 (67.7)

Table 4. COHORT B for SECONDARY ANALYSIS: Characteristics of patients by Economic Instability outcome INCLUDING change or loss of insurance in Long COVID positive group

Figure 7 (below) shows the results of a logistic regression that includes demographic information as independent variables and examines how they impact Economic Instability post covid among the Long COVID patients (COHORT B). See the discussion section of this report for observations about these results.

Figure 7: GEEGLM model forest plots for secondary analysis (COHORT B)

The statistical analysis shown in Figure 8 (below) is similar to that represented by Figure 7, except that the feature set used in the Figure 8 analysis also includes Social Determinants of Health and a rurality flag (based on the patient's zip code) as independent variables in examining how they impact new Economic Instability in the Long COVID sub-cohort. See the discussion section of this report for observations about these results.

Figure 8: GEEGLM model forest plots for secondary analysis (COHORT-B) with SDoH

Discussion

In this discussion we are reviewing trends noted in each of the feature tables as well as the results of each the GEEGLM models. We also discuss overall trends and consideration for future work.

Primary Analysis (58 sites): Economic Instability (New disability, food instability, or housing instability)

The question posed was: among patients with known COVID-19, who is experiencing new Economic Instability?

COVID-19 Positive (Cohort A)

Review of Descriptive Statistics (Table 1)

Among our new Economic Instability features the most common was Housing Instability and least Food Insecurity. When compared to the group without new Economic Instability, the patient population with any new documented Economic Instability post-COVID is characterized by more males, children and patients above 50, and patients with recorded race/ethnicity as Black or African American or Hispanic or Latino. For patients with an available zip code, we have added Census derived SDoH variables and a rural flag. The group with new Economic Instability appears to be slightly more rural based on patient zip codes.

Review of Statistical Analysis (Figures 1 and 2)

After having controlled for different sites and all covariates using GEEGLM models, we see that all non-White race/ethnicity categories are associate with a higher odds of Economic Instability. These relationships are statistically significant (p -value $< .05$) and are mostly unchanged when we limit to patients with zip and control for rurality and area-level SDoH features. Rural home addresses also emerge as a strong predictor for new Economic Instability. Because all age groups (except for 60-69 for which the odds ratio is NOT statistically significant) show a lower odds ratio for Economic Instability, no particular age emerges as a strong predictor once we control for other covariates.

Long COVID Positive (COHORT B)

Review of Descriptive Statistics (Table 2)

When we focus our analysis on only the COVID positive patients with documented Long COVID, we see some similar patterns in Table 2 as we did in Table 1 with Housing Instability being the most common new Economic Instability and Food Insecurity the least. A higher overall percentage of this Long COVID cohort (1.9%) has documented new Economic Instability than in the COVID positive group at large (0.4%). When compared to the Long COVID group without new Economic Instability, the patient population with any new documented Economic Instability post-COVID is characterized

by more Black or African American, male, and age from 50-69. Note that we tend to always see fewer patients in the >70 age group when looking at documented Long COVID populations, but this may be because older patients are less likely to pursue care for lingering COVID symptoms. As in the general COVID positive population, the Long COVID group with new Economic Instability appears to be more rural based on their zip codes.

Review of Statistical Analysis (Figures 3 and 4)

After having controlled for different sites and all covariates using GEEGLM models, we again see that all non-White race/ethnicity categories are associated with higher odds of Economic Instability. Because this analysis focuses on the smaller Long COVID sub-cohort, only the Black or African American group has an odds ratio with a statistically significant probability (p -value $<.05$). When we limit to patients with zip and control for area-level SDoH features, the higher odds ratio for Hispanic or Latinos does also become statistically significant. We also see male sex and rural home address as statistically significant predictors of new Economic Instability.

Secondary Analysis (16 sites): Economic Instability (Includes above features plus change from private insurance to Medicaid or loss of INSURANCE)

This is similar to the primary analyses, but includes “Change in insurance payor (private pay to Medicaid) or loss of insurance” as an outcome along with the combined Economic Instability outcomes in the primary analysis. In order to study this outcome, we further restricted sites to those that report the insurance type associated with each patient visit in their N3C data.

COVID Positive (COHORT A)

Review of Descriptive Statistics (Table 3)

When we focus our analysis on sites that report insurance data, Table 3 shows that in their COVID positive patients, Change to Medicaid or Loss of Insurance (98%) is by far the most common new Economic Instability. Therefore, in this analysis, new Economic Instability is almost entirely represented by this insurance outcome. When new Economic Instability includes Change to Medicaid or Loss of Insurance also appears at a much greater frequency (17% of cohort) than the basic new Economic Instability variable. When compared to the group without new Economic Instability, the patient population with any new documented Economic Instability post-COVID is characterized by more adults up to age 69, and, once again, more patients with recorded race/ethnicity as Black or African American or Hispanic or Latino. Note that when we include change/loss of insurance as an Economic Instability feature, more women and fewer rural patients are in the new Economic Instability group, both of which are a change from our primary analysis.

Review of Statistical Analysis (Figures 5 and 6)

After having controlled for different sites and all covariates using GEEGLM models, we again see that Black or African American and Hispanic or Latino reported race/ethnicity values are associated with a higher odds of Economic Instability, although this time we see adult age groups dominating the model. The change/loss of insurance outcome has lower odds for males and for Asian Non-Hispanics which are different from what we saw with the new Economic Instability outcomes in the primary analysis. Few relationships change when we limit to patients with zip and control for area-level SDoH features, except that the odds ratio for Black or African Americans drops just below one. Note that ALL odds ratios in both these analyses (with and without SDOH features) are statistically significant (p -value $< .05$) and have much tighter confidence intervals, likely due to a better balance between those with new Economic Instability (largely based on change/loss of insurance) and those without new Economic Instability.

Long COVID Positive (COHORT B)

Review of Descriptive Statistics (Table 4)

When we focus our change or loss of insurance analysis on only the COVID positive patients with documented Long COVID, we see some similar patterns in Table 4 as we did in Table 3. Note that an even higher percentage of this population (29%) has a Change to Medicaid or Loss of Insurance.

Review of Statistical Analysis (Figures 7 and 8)

After having controlled for different sites and all covariates using GEEGLM models, we again see the middle age features dominating. This is the only model where Black or African American and Hispanic or Latino have an odds ratio close to one, although this time they do NOT have a statistically significant p -value and their confidence intervals cross one, meaning that we cannot make much of a determination about those features in this particular analysis. Similarly, when we limit to patients with zip and control for area-level SDoH features, we also see the rural feature with an odds ratio < 1 for the first time, but it is also not statistically significant so this shift should be discounted. When controlling for SDoH features, Hispanic or Latino patients do again have higher odds of the change/loss of insurance and the p -value is again statistically significant. Note that Black or African American continues to be the highest predictor of new Economic Instability for Long COVID patients, even when controlling for SDoH.

TRENDS OBSERVED:

In general, it is important to note that the demographic features associated with new Economic Instability when we look at percentages alone (in our feature tables) are not always statistically significant once we control for site and run models where these features are alongside other covariates. Therefore it is critical to look at the model results when drawing our conclusions. It is also important to note that running multiple similar analyses allows us to look for features that are important across models. These are the trends we observe when we look across all the analyses:

- 1) **Black or African American Non Hispanics and Hispanic or Latino race/ethnicity values (as recorded in the medical record) were consistently high with new Economic Instability post-COVID** across our primary analyses. This held true for all statistically significant odds ratios and when controlling for other factors like age, sex, zip code level social determinants of health and Long COVID sub-phenotype. In our secondary analyses, which included the subset of sites with insurance data, the Black or African American Non Hispanic and Hispanic or Latino features again showed higher odds ratio for new Economic Instability, but in this case the odds ratios did shift in the sub-analyses where we added SDoH and rural features. The odds ratio for Asian Non-Hispanic was less consistent, as we saw it sometimes below one and sometimes above one. Note that the White Non-Hispanic features are included in the base case for the intercept in these models which means it is the race/ethnicity category against which we are comparing the others.
- 2) We see that the features of **age 50-59 and 60-69** are predictors of new Economic Instability across all analyses (whenever the odds ratios are statistically significant with p-value >0.05). Age features are particularly predictive in the models that include Change to Medicaid or Loss of Insurance. There is some variability in the 70+ population which may be attributed to either social security and Medicare resources available. Further Medicare-based analysis would be needed to confirm this theory. We see some other age groups emerging with high odds ratios in some models, but with less consistency than the 50-69 age group.
- 3) The insurance-dependent data was included only in a separate sub-analysis due to the fact that not all sites included this type of data. We noted that the majority of COVID patients who had a documented **change from private insurance to Medicaid** post-COVID also experienced **a loss of insurance** post-COVID (approximately 60%). This makes sense because events related to loss of insurance could certainly result in someone qualifying for Medicaid. Because of this overlap, we combined the two into a single variable: change from private insurance to Medicaid or loss of insurance post-COVID. When we added that variable to the new Economic Instability feature we saw that it is much more prevalent than the other Economic Instability features we studied. However, the overall patterns continue to emerge, suggesting that certain subpopulations are particularly vulnerable to experiencing Economic Instability post-COVID.
- 4) We recognize that Long COVID is under-reported in the COVID positive population, but it is still interesting to look within the Long COVID population for trends and compare

them to the COVID positive group at large. In doing so we **see higher rates of new Economic Instability in the patients with documented Long COVID**. When all the features are included in the Long COVID sub-cohort models, we see similar odds ratios associated with each feature, with some loss of significance due to lower patient counts.

- 5) It is very interesting that in every model where we included **area-level Social Determinants of Health (census data linked to the patient using ZCTA to ZIP crosswalk)** these features are not themselves predictive of new Economic Instability as their odds ratios stay very close to 1. It was important to include these variables to determine if differences in race/ethnicity were just a proxy for area-level Economic Instability. We only observe one case (mentioned in part 1 above) where adding these features resulted in the odds ratio for Black or African American dropping slightly below 1.
- 6) Sub-phenotypes for Long COVID were included in order to determine whether certain clusters were associated with more Long COVID. We did not see results to suggest that any such patterns can be defined by the clusters we chose. **Further work is required to continue sub-phenotyping in Long COVID** (through collaboration between the prospective PASC RECOVER researchers and our observational EHR research teams) after which we may rerun our models using new information. However, these clusters remain important features in our model, helping to establish that the above trends remain true after controlling for our known subphenotypes.
- 7) The flag for rural is generated based on patient zip code based on the definition provided above and the values in supplemental table 1. When this covariate is added to the models, it always appears to be predictive of new Economic Instability (except for one model where its p-value is not statistically significant). **This suggests that patients living in rural areas are particularly vulnerable to new Economic Instability post-COVID.**

Appendix Table 1: Primary RUCA codes, 2010

Code	Classification description
1	Metropolitan area core: primary flow within an urbanized area (UA)
2	Metropolitan area high commuting: primary flow 30% or more to a UA
3	Metropolitan area low commuting: primary flow 10% to 30% to a UA
4	Micropolitan area core: primary flow within an urban cluster of 10,000 to 49,999 (large UC)
5	Micropolitan high commuting: primary flow 30% or more to a large UC
6	Micropolitan low commuting: primary flow 10% to 30% to a large UC
7	Small town core: primary flow within an urban cluster of 2,500 to 9,999 (small UC)
8	Small town high commuting: primary flow 30% or more to a small UC
9	Small town low commuting: primary flow 10% to 30% to a small UC
10	Rural areas: primary flow to a tract outside a UA or UC
99	Not coded: Census tract has zero population and no rural-urban identifier information

Concept IDs for Economic Instability codes

Economic Instability codes	
Concept ID	Concept name
494017259	Disability
79249672	Housing Instability: Part 1 (Flagged Conditions)
679238231	Housing Instability: Part 2 (Survey and/or Query)
650794217	Housing Instability: Part 3 (Survey/Query Response Values)
831413313	Food_Insecurity_PASC

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